

Mechanical characterization of Glass Fibre-Reinforced Air Lime-Based Mortars

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Abstract. The basic issue in determining the deformational properties of masonry is to conduct a comprehensive experimental characterization of the masonry components' materials, including their mechanical properties. This characterization process is even more important for new sustainable mortar solutions, especially in the context of strengthening and renovating existing masonry buildings, including historic structures. The work presents and discusses the mechanical tests carried out on a mixed cement-lime mortar based on air lime and reinforced with the addition of industrial glass fibres. Mechanical testing on prisms (40 × 40 × 160 mm) and cylinders (60 diameter × 120 mm height) demonstrated the beneficial impact of fibres in the mortar mixture analysed specifically in terms of improved compressive, flexural and splitting post-peak behaviour.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, the scientific community and building construction industry are showing an increasing interest for sustainable building materials that can combine adequate mechanical strength, improved durability, and compatibility with existing structures. Within this context, the utilization of composite materials, which have been widely employed in retrofitting operations for the improvement of masonry structures to seismic codes [1-2], is emerging as a highly promising solution.

Several composite materials are available for enhancing and repairing existing masonry structures, primarily used as reinforcing plasters. These materials include: fibre reinforced polymers (FRP) [3], fabric reinforced cementitious matrices/textile reinforced mortars (FRCM/TRM) [4-5] and fibre reinforced mortar (FRM) [6-7]. Among these options, FRM offers a good trade-off between compatibility with masonry substrates, increased mechanical properties, and rapid application [8], while also considering sustainability through the utilization of natural fibres [9-10].

While most applications focus on cement and hydraulic mortars with natural and industrial fibres at the mortar and masonry level, there is limited research on air lime-based mortars containing fibre additions. In this context, Khalaf et al. [11] studied the influence of the mechanical properties on pure cement mortar adding two different fibre lengths: 20mm

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and 30mm in three different proportions: 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75 % by volume of the mix. The flexural and compressive strength is subjected to an improvement for all the proportions that is inversely proportional to the length of the fibres. However, Chawla et al. [12] noted in their study on FRC with increasing proportions of glass fibres of 12 mm, a peak for the maximum compressive strength obtainable by increasing the fibre content and after a decrease of the improvement due to further fibre content addition. More recently, Małek et al. [13] tested cement-based mortars with glass fibres having length of about 49 mm with increasing waste glass fibre contents from (600 to 1800 g/m³) but keeping a constant water-cement ratio adding low-alkaline liquid chemical admixture. While the elastic modulus of reinforced samples and Poisson ratio did not vary greatly, air content, compressive strength, tensile splitting and flexural strength of reinforced samples increased with the fibre content almost linearly with different gradients. Recycled glass fibres were tested by Zhou et al. [14] showing how the chemical and physical properties had an impact on mechanical performance improvement. In their study, they found that the length ranging from 6mm to 20 mm and length/width ratio higher than 6 have a better behaviour in improving the cement mortars. Together with the improvement of the mechanical properties glass fibres reinforced cement-based materials have a superior cost that is balanced by their lower environmental impacts than concrete [15] and within the reinforcing fibres for cement composites glass fibres acts better than polyvinyl alcohol fibres and virgin carbon fibres, based on multicriteria life cycle assessment performed by Akbar et al. [16].

Regarding properly air lime-based mortars, Stefanidou et al. [17] studied the effect of aerial lime type CL-80 with industrial fibres on the mechanical properties with the optimal outcome for carbon types. Later, Kesikidou and Stefanidou [18] worked on pure air lime and cement mortars reinforced with jute, coconut and kelp fibres in 1.5% of weight. Both mortar types increased their flexural strength and fracture energy with more elevated percentages for lime mortars. Anyway, reinforced cement mortars noted a decrease of the compressive strength while reinforced lime mortars showed relevant improvement for all the fibres, with a maximum of around 360% for kelp fibres. In the same context of sustainability applications, Barrios et al. [19] compared CL-70 air hydrated lime with cement mortars and natural or recycled ceramic aggregates with different fibre additions. On one hand, incorporating glass fibres led to a decrease of shrinkage of modified mortars with recycled aggregates, but on the other hand, it was observed that the mechanical properties were reduced in comparison to mortars containing natural aggregates. An improvement of the behaviour in relation to shrinkage deformation was also found by Izaguirre et al. [20] in lime mortars with two different proportions of polypropylene fibres.

Effectively, the utilization of hydraulic lime instead of air lime in the binder can lead to significant distinctions due to their unique hardening processes: hydraulic lime cures through hydration, whereas air lime cures via carbonation [21]. Furthermore, in addition to variances in binders and fibres, the interaction between the matrix, sand, and fibres, including factors such as sand granulometry and potential fillers, can impact the mechanical performance of mortar mixes [22], an aspect that has not been comprehensively addressed in some previous studies [8-9, 23]. Additionally, in the context of large-scale masonry interventions, there are few experimental studies where it was opted for fibre-reinforced mortars based on air lime as a reinforced plaster. For instance, Bustos-Garcia et al. [24] conducted experiments involving masonry wallettes subjected to diagonal compression. These experiments utilized different coating solutions, including layers of cement and mixed cement-air lime with the addition of glass fibres (0.5% in volume of the mix). While wallettes coated with reinforced cement mortar exhibited superior shear strength, those coated with reinforced mixed mortars demonstrated higher deformation capacity until failure, suggesting the potential efficacy of these mortars. Specifically, for masonry heritage interventions, attention must be given not solely to mechanical aspects [25], but also to the physical and mineralogical properties [26].

This ensures the selection of a reinforcing material that is compatible as closely as possible with the historical materials.

In this study, experimental characterization of glass fibres reinforced air lime-based mortars is carried out using destructive techniques for understanding their macroscale properties. Mechanical tests on one type of plain mortar and its reinforced counterpart with glass fibres are performed to determine their compressive, splitting tensile and flexural strength, as well as fracture energy differences.

2 Experimental programme

2.1 Materials

The materials used for preparing the two mortars are: air lime CL90-S [27], cement CEM II/B-32.5 R [28] and siliceous sand of grading 0/2 mm with granulometry shown in fig. 1. Mortar mix proportions are given in mass quantity in Table 1. Specifically, two mixes are considered: mix P without fibres and mix P-F reinforced with fibres. The mass proportions for these mixes were selected based on experimental experiences [8-9]. The mixtures consisted of 65% sand and 35% binder of the total product, with the binder composed of 30% air lime and 70% cement by mass. Definitely, the mass proportions of cement, lime, and sand were 0.7:0.3:1.85. For the reinforced mortar, alkali-resistant glass fibres with density 2.68 g/cm³ were added to the mix at 0.75% of the weight of the mix. The length and diameter of the fibres are 12 mm and 0.014 mm, while the elastic modulus and tensile strength, declared by the producer, are 72GPa and not inferior to 1000 MPa, respectively. The water-to-binder ratio was adjusted to achieve suitable workability for plain mortar. The same amount of water was then used for the reinforced mortar to evaluate changes in the slump due only the fibre addition, as determined by the flow table test EN 1015-3 [29] (fig.2).

Fig. 1. Sieve curve of the adopted sand.

Table 1. Mortar mixes composition considered in this study.

Mixes	Cement [g]	Lime [g]	Sand [g]	Water [g]	Fibres [g]
P	509	218	1350	312	-
P-F	509	218	1350	312	16

Fig. 2. Slump differences for the same water amount added to the mortars.

For both mortar mixes analysed, all the specimens were cast after 30 seconds of vibration and cured according to the conditions specified in EN 1015-11 [30]. Specifically, the mortar specimens were maintained at a temperature of $20\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a humidity level of $65\%\pm 5\%$ for 21 days, following an initial 7 days of curing in polyethylene bags, before being tested at 28 days.

2.2 Test methods

A summary of the mechanical tests carried out for the material characterization of the two mortars is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Test summary relative to each mix.

Test type	Shape	Dimension [mm]	Number of Samples
Flexural	prism	$40 \times 40 \times 160$	3
Compressive	half prism	$40 \times 40 \times \sim 80$	6
Compressive	cylinder	60×120	5
Splitting	cylinder	60×120	6
Fracture energy	prism	$40 \times 40 \times 160$	5

First, three points bending tests were conducted on mortar prisms of dimension $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm, in accordance with EN 1015-11 [30]. The samples were subjected to an increasing concentrated force at the midpoint of a 100 mm span of the prisms until failure. Three specimens for both mixes were tested with a load control test set up working at a speed of 0.05 kN/s. The resulting six half prisms from each mortar mix were tested in compression according to EN 1015-11 [30] at the same load speed. Axial compression was ensured by using square-shaped steel plates measuring 40×40 mm and applying a uniform vertical load. View of the test set-ups for prism flexural and half-prism compressive test is given in fig. 3a-b.

Fig. 3 Flexural (a) and compressive (b) test set-ups for prisms according to EN 1015-11 [24].
Example from mortar with fibre.

Compressive tests were also performed on cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 60 mm and a height of 120 mm. A displacement control test setup with a load rate of 0.05 mm/s was used to investigate the compressive behaviour. The axial-vertical displacement was measured using a digital image correlation (DIC) system, which also detected the initiation and development of cracks in the samples. Measurements of the elastic modulus E_c were assumed considering the slope of the compressive stress-strain curves between the values of the 30% and 50% of the peak compressive strength. At the same time, displacement control set up permitted to obtain information on the post-peak behaviour of the samples in terms of ductility μ , quantified as the ratio of the strain at a drop of 75% of peak load in the softening branch to the strain at the peak load. View of the cylindric compressive test set-up is given in fig 4.

Fig. 4. Cylindrical compressive test set-up with camera from DIC system. Example from mortar without fibre.

Splitting tensile tests on cylindrical samples were also conducted using cylinders with the same dimensions as those used for compression tests. A displacement control system with a loading rate of 0.01 mm/s was employed, applying the vertical load along the diameter of the cylinders by means of a flat steel bar. The procedure of this test aligned with the standard procedure ASTM C496 [31] with test set-up shown in fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Splitting test set up adopted in this study. Example from mortar without fibre.

Fracture energy tests were conducted using the same three-point bending test setup as the previously described flexural tests, but with differences in the loading protocol. Standard prisms measuring $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm were utilized, featuring notches with dimensions of 3 mm thickness and 6 mm depth. These notch dimensions were selected based on experimental tests [8-9] to assess the fracture energy of reinforced hydraulic lime mortars, which typically exhibit lower strength compared to concrete. Apart from the specimen dimensions, the RILEM FMC-50 [32] standard was followed, with specimens subjected to increasing loads at a displacement rate of 0.001 mm/s. Picture of the typical specimen ready to be tested in the machine with test set-up details is given in fig. 6. The fracture energy calculation is given according to the following relationship (1), where W is the area under the load-deflection curve, mS/L is the weight of the beam between the supports where m is the total weight of the beam, and S and L denote the length of the support (100 mm) and the total length (160 mm) of the beam, g is the gravity acceleration, δ is the failure beam deflection, d is the beam height (40 mm), b is the beam width (40 mm) and a is the notch depth.

$$Gf = (W + mS/L g \delta) / (d - a) b \quad (1)$$

Fig. 6. Fracture energy test set-up. Example from mortar without fibre.

3 Results

Table 3 shows the average values of flexural strength and compressive strength for both plain and reinforced mixes. For mortar P, the compressive strength is 14.06 MPa (13.54%) and the flexural strength is 2.83 MPa (9.40%), with coefficients of variation in brackets. The reinforced mortar P-F exhibits lower values of both compressive strength and flexural strength with 12.62 MPa (8.54%) and 2.29 MPa (10.25%), respectively. In both mortars, with and without fibres, the failure mode initiated and progressed in the middle cross-section. In the failed samples with fibres, an irregular fibre distribution along the central cross-section was observed. (Fig. 7a-b). In the compression tests, half prisms of mortar mix P exhibited a conical failure shape with material expulsion from the lateral surfaces. The reinforced mortar displayed a similar crack pattern, but the material expulsion was limited, resulting in the failed samples remaining almost intact at the point of failure (Fig. 8a-b).

Figures 9a-b shows the results of compressive axial stress-axial strains for the cylindrical samples of both mortar mixes. Consistent with the tests conducted on half prisms, reinforced mortar showed an inferior average compressive strength. Average values of compressive strength f_{cc} , elastic modulus E_c and post-peak ductility μ of both mixes are given in table 4.

Table 3. Flexural and compressive test result according to EN 1015-11 [30].

Mixes	Flexural strength [MPa] (CoV)	Compressive strength [MPa] (CoV)
P	2.83 (9.40)	14.06 (13.54)
P-F	2.29 (10.25)	12.62 (8.54)

Fig. 7. Crack formation in the middle cross-section for 3-point bending test of mortar P (a) and mortar P-F (b).

The failure modes for both mixes exhibited conical and split tensile failures, which never led to complete disaggregation of the materials (Fig. 10a-b). Additionally, the integrity of the samples was largely maintained, indicating a degree of material cohesion even at the point of failure.

Fig. 8. Crack formation in the half prism compression tests for mortar P (a) and mortar P-F (b).

Table 4. Average values of compressive strength results from cylindric tests.

Mixes	fcc [MPa] (CoV)	Ec [MPa] (CoV)	μ [-] (CoV)
P	9.29 (9.58)	1107.48 (28.63)	1.14 (8.23)
P-F	7.56 (13.83)	1179.99 (5.02)	1.62 (13.48)

Fig. 9. Compressive axial stress-strain for mortar mix P (a) and reinforced mortar P-F (b). Each colour represents a sample.

Fig. 10. Failed cylindrical samples in compression for mortar mix P (a) and reinforced mortar mix P-F (b).

In the cylindrical splitting tests, the average tensile strength for mix P and mix P-F was 0.76 MPa (21.35%) and 0.90 MPa (11.73%), respectively. While the post-peak behaviour of the plain mix displayed a brittle failure, the reinforced mix generally exhibited ductile characteristics in its post-peak tensile behaviour (Fig. 11a-b). The failure modes were consistent across all analysed samples, with the cylinders typically splitting into two parts along their loading diameter (Fig. 12a-b).

Fig. 11. Splitting tensile stress-vertical displacement for mortar mix P **(a)** and reinforced mortar mix P-F **(b)**. Each colour represents a sample.

For the fracture energy test, the relationships between vertical load and deflection of the samples are shown in Fig. 13. The switch from load control to a more precise and time-consuming displacement control test setup revealed differences from the previous three-point bending test on samples of the same dimensions. Notably, this approach highlighted higher deflections and peak loads for mortar mix P-F compared to the fibre-free mortar mix P. Values of the fracture energy according to RILEM FMC-50 [32] standard shows values of 39.25 N/m (11.27) for mix P and 535.30 (27.64) for mix P-F. As expected, no differences in the failure modes of both mortars from this set-up and the previous ones were evidenced (fig. 14a-b).

Fig. 12. Failed samples from the splitting tests of mortar mix P **(a)** and reinforced mortar mix P-F **(b)**.

Fig. 13. Load deflection curves for fracture energy evaluation for mix P (a) and reinforced mortar mix P-F (b).

Fig. 14. Failed samples of reinforced mortar mix P-F (a) and detail of cross-section for unreinforced mortar mix P (b).

4 Discussion

The inclusion of glass fibre in the mixture impacts both its fresh and mechanical properties. In this context, the calibration of the water content for the mixes assume even more importance influencing the mechanical properties of the hardened mixes and their workability [33]. Specifically, for the fresh properties, adding the same amount of water to the fibre-reinforced mix resulted in a 10.06% reduction in slump value compared to the mix without fibre. Several authors [8-9] in their analysis of the mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced mortars adopt a mix design choice that uses fixed amounts of additives. In contrast, Malek et al. [13] proposed maintaining a constant water-to-binder ratio by increasing the quantity of additives as the fibre content in the mix increases. It is important to keep in mind that adding additives to improve workability generally reduces the sustainability of mortar mixes, as it increases their carbon footprint when assessed through a life cycle analysis (LCA) [34].

Regarding the mechanical properties, both the compressive strength measured on half prisms and cylinders showed the same pattern with a decrease of compressive strength in the reinforced mix. Specifically, the average compressive strength measured on half prisms shows a reduction of 10.28%, while the cylindrical compressive strength decreases by 18.69%. This aspect, which necessitates further analysis, may be attributed a part to the differences in the test setup loading protocols but also to the different redistribution of fibres

in prisms and cylinders. For instance, Gettu et al. [35] have noted that in steel fibre reinforced concrete (SFRC), vibration promotes the horizontal alignment of fibres, which is beneficial for prisms but may not be appropriate for cylinders. Anyway, as expected, the compressive strength of the half prisms is higher than that of the cylinders due to the different stress states and the greater platen confinement exerted on the squat samples [36]. The ratio of the average cylindrical compressive strength to the average half prism compressive strength is 0.66 for mortar mix P and 0.60 for reinforced mortar P-F. Additionally, the addition of fibres does not appear to affect the elastic modulus of the reinforced mix P-F, although it reduces its scatter compared to mortar without fibres. No improvement in the compressive elastic modulus was observed in similar mortar mixes [8-9,23], regardless of the ratio used for calculation. This could be because fibre lengths exceeding 6 mm are too long to effectively counteract initial micro-cracking. The most significant positive effect of fibre addition is the enhancement of post-peak behaviour in cylindrical compressive strength. Specifically, the post-peak ductility of the fibre-reinforced mix improves by 41.61%, increasing its deformation capacity.

A similar pattern is observed in the splitting tensile tests, where the post-peak behaviour exhibits an elasto-plastic response after reaching peak tensile strength in reinforced mixes, whereas the unreinforced mix typically demonstrates a brittle failure after the peak. Additionally, the splitting tensile strength is enhanced in the reinforced mortar by 18.57% in this case.

The observed flexural behaviour shows contrasting results. In load-controlled three-point bending tests, a decrease in flexural strength is noted for the reinforced mix P-F. However, in displacement-controlled three-point bending tests used to evaluate fracture energy, the reinforced mortar exhibits higher average flexural strength values. This inconsistency, which also requires additional investigation, is likely attributable to several factors. These include probably an insufficient number of samples tested in load control, where three samples represent the minimum requirement according to EN 1015-11 [30] for masonry mortars but not for reinforced ones. Additionally, an excessively high speed may have led to elevated flexural strength values in load control [37-38]. Taking into account the results of the flexural behaviour under displacement control, which generally provides more accurate measurements, and consistent with the results of the tensile splitting tests, the flexural strength at the mid-span of the notched prisms is 1.89 MPa (14.54) for mix P and 2.23 MPa (15.34) for the reinforced mortar. This represents a 17.88% increase in flexural strength compared to the unreinforced mix. Additionally, the fracture energy for the reinforced mix shows a significant increase, being 13.63 times higher. Similarly, Mercuri et al. [23], in their tests on mixed hydraulic lime-cement mortars with and without polyvinyl-alcohol (PVA) fibres, observed a substantial increase in fracture energy. Specifically, for the mix containing 12 mm fibres at 0.75% of the mass as per our testing, there was an approximate increase of 28.6 times in fracture energy from the unreinforced to reinforced samples. Mercuri et al. [23] also observed an increase in compressive strength with the addition of more fibres to the mix, a result that was not evident in our tests.

5 Conclusions

This study presents experimental results on the mechanical characterization of a mixed cement-air lime mortar and its counterpart mix, where a fixed amount of glass fibres is added without altering the water-to-binder ratio. The mechanical characterization consisted in the evaluation of flexural, compressive and splitting tensile strength as well as fracture energy. To evaluate the post-peak characteristics of the mixes, compressive strength tests were conducted on cylinders in addition to the standard prisms. Similarly, the flexural strength of

the prisms was also measured using a displacement control test setup. Based on the analysis of the test results, the following conclusions can be made:

- Fibre addition significantly reduces the workability of the mix, making it more challenging to handle. This decrease in workability may necessitate the use of additional water or superplasticizers to achieve the desired consistency and ease of application.
- The addition of fibres does not appear to enhance the peak compressive strength or alter the elastic modulus of the mortar. However, it significantly improves the post-peak behaviour, resulting in a 41.61% increase in post-peak ductility.
- Fibre addition appears to enhance the peak splitting tensile strength of cylinders by approximately 19%. Furthermore, the addition of fibres modifies the post-peak splitting tensile behaviour, shifting it from brittle to more plastic.
- Fibre addition significantly enhances the flexural behaviour of the mix, particularly by increasing the deflection capacity of the prisms and, consequently, the fracture energy. The fracture energy values of the reinforced mix are approximately 14 times higher than those of the plain mix.

Further research is needed to explore how the mechanical response of various air lime mortar mixes is affected by incorporating different quantities, types, and dimensions of fibres. Additionally, it would be beneficial to investigate how altering the sand granulometry in a specific reinforced mortar may impact the distribution of fibres within the mix and subsequently influence the mechanical response. Moreover, conducting comprehensive multi-scale investigations into physical properties is essential to understand the nature of the bond between the fibres and the mortar matrix. This approach can also help clarify changes in porosity and the packing of grains, which may affect the mechanical behaviour of the mortar and therefore provide insights to optimize the strength of reinforced mixes.

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